

**SOME MODERN TECHNOLOGIES OF TEACHING
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Abstract. This article talks about the importance and necessity of learning English. The need to use different methods and technologies in learning and teaching English, as well as the main methods of teaching English are considered.

Keywords: educational process, technologies, teaching methods, education system, English language.

The construction of the educational process in the classroom includes the active use of modern educational technologies, taking into account modern requirements for the quality of education and the level of formation of educational activities.

The concept of using modern educational technologies in English classes is based on the principles and methods of competency-based education, technologies of personality-oriented and developmental education, and strategies and techniques for teaching semantic reading and working with text.

Considering that classrooms often contain students with different levels of language proficiency, it would be advisable to use a variety of modern educational technologies. Pedagogical (educational) technology is a model of joint educational and pedagogical activities thought out in every detail to design, organize and conduct the educational process, ensuring comfortable conditions for students and teachers. Pedagogical technology involves the implementation of the idea of complete controllability of the educational process.

Criteria for modern educational technologies

Before choosing a technology, you should identify the requirements that it must meet:

☑ Systematic

Modern technologies for teaching English should contain such characteristics of a system as the logic of the process, the integrity and interconnection of individual parts;

☑ Conceptuality

Any technology must consist of a scientific concept that contains justification for achieving educational goals from the psychological and socio-pedagogical side;

☑ Efficiency

The technology must guarantee a result that meets educational standards;

☑ Flexibility

The technology should allow for the ability to vary depending on the comfort and interaction of students with the teacher;

☑ Dynamicity

The selected technology always has the prospect of further development or transformation;

☑ Reproducibility

Any technology must be understandable so that it can be used by different teachers and students in other educational institutions.

Types of modern educational technologies

1. Communicative - designed to develop skills of communicative competence. These modern technologies in English lessons are necessary for students to adapt to the forms and models of communication in modern cultures.

2. Differentiated technology - knowledge of the subject is carried out taking into account their personal interests, skills and strengths. Capacity development is based on encouragement as well as the use of diagnostic tests.

3. Modular technology - provides that a modern English lesson, as well as its content (autonomous modules, subsections) are integrated into one general course.

4. Information and communication technologies - provides for increasing the practical orientation of the lesson, as well as increasing cognitive activity by increasing the intensity of students' independent work.

5. Technology using software is a subtype of ICT. Such technologies for teaching English effectively complement the process of learning to translate texts. This technology is characterized by the use of computer programs that intensify the independent activity of students. This helps develop grammar, vocabulary and machine translation skills.

6. Internet technologies - open up various opportunities and accesses for finding information, creating individual projects and research.

7. Modern technologies in teaching English on the basis of individual training - implements a student-oriented teaching method, which takes into account the interests and characteristics of students.

8. Testing technology - based on monitoring students' assimilation of material within the course. These teaching technologies in English lessons allow the teacher to identify the strengths and weaknesses of students, as well as identify shortcomings in his program. International English language exams are held in accordance with modern testing technologies.

9. Project technology - characterized by the creation of a model of social interaction between students. This technique promotes the formation of interdisciplinary connections that improve the overall performance of students.

10. Collaboration-based technology exploits the idea of collaborative learning. In this case, a separate role is assigned to both personal and collective responsibility for achieving the designated goals.

11. Game technology - is based on unlocking the potential and developing the creative thinking of students during joint consideration and solution of assigned problems. For example, by using the popular game "Broken Phone," students develop the skill of consecutive or simultaneous translation.

12. Technology for the development of critical thinking - designed to develop in the student a versatile person who can be critical and attentive to the information received.

This technology becomes extremely relevant in the literary translation of works of art, poems, etc.

Due to the fact that in each class there are immediately differences in the level of learning among students, I consider the technology of intraclass differentiation with the addition of elements of multi-level learning to be the most acceptable and relevant in organizing the educational process. Taking into account the typological characteristics of each student, they are divided into conditional groups "A", "B", "C". Techniques of collective work are used, in dynamic pairs or groups. Group "C" tasks are fixed as a basic standard—minimal or reproductive. Here, multiple repetitions are highlighted, lexical supports are highlighted. Tasks "B" are built at an analytical-synthetic level and provide the mental activity that is necessary to solve application tasks. Group A tasks involve a creative or productive level. Students consciously and creatively apply their knowledge, composing mini-dialogues and monologues on the topic. Elements of organizing a group form of work make it possible to intensify the cognitive activity of students in class and to include each student in the learning process. Within the groups, everyone can express their opinion and actively participate in the decision of educational programs, in accordance with the level of language training and the lexical units studied. At each lesson, didactic material of varying

complexity is created. All this gives a tangible educational result. Students who have insufficient knowledge, who have poor command of spoken language, cease to be shy; on the contrary, they try to follow the strong ones, enter into dialogue more easily, correct their mistakes in constructing a conversation, try to express their thoughts monologically, and learn to formulate questions.

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